

COUNCIL ON
LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
THIRTY-FOURTH
ANNUAL REPORT/1990

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine* . . . Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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6. Beginning May 1990.

7. September 1989 - June 1990.

PROGRAM REVIEW

Introduction

This report records CLR program activities for 1989/90. While each year (this is the Council's thirty-fourth) differs from its predecessors, the changes are subtle because programs are not naturally segmented into annual cycles. New ventures begin, others end, still others go on, year in and year out, reminding us that progress in complex matters still comes one step at a time. Persistence, one correspondent recently wrote, is one of our most visible characteristics. Another is the steadily growing level of direct involvement of CLR's small staff in many of our most important undertakings. In essence, CLR often serves as both the funder and the manager for continuing projects, especially when the means to accomplish objectives are not clear and must evolve. Several of these CLR-managed projects are described in this report.

The Council continues making grants as well, with most awards going to librarians who seek financial support in the context of one or another of the programs available to individuals with active professional interests at different stages of their careers. While the number of active grants in a given year is relatively stable, the number of proposals received fluctuates widely.

The concern that there are too few proposals from librarians surfaces annually and we look for new ways to stimulate interest. Because of a declining number of applications, the CLR Academic Library Management Intern Program and the Cooperative Research Program were reviewed during the spring of 1990. In both cases the programs and their results got high marks, but aside from the acknowledged need for more publicity, there were few promising suggestions of ways to increase participation. The logical conclusion—not an especially encouraging one—is that only a small portion of active librarians in academic and public libraries are inclined (or encouraged) to pursue professional interests beyond specific job requirements. Whether this situation reflects a workforce that is overloaded or one that undervalues the importance of an expanding and dynamic intellectual foundation for its work is not clear, but it is a symptom that needs attention.

A status report on several CLR-managed projects and a record of grants made during the year follow. Together they provide an overview of the CLR program for 1989/90.

CLR-Managed Projects

When it serves as project manager, the Council, as an operating foundation, not only provides funds but enlists participants and serves as the secretariat. During the past year, four important projects have dominated staff efforts, three of them part of the ongoing CLR research program for library planning and operations and the fourth related to evolving Council interests in professional education. Participants in each of these projects are identified in an appendix to this program report.

I. Professional Education

Two committees have concerned themselves with professional education during the year. The first, a small Working Committee on Library Education, met several times during the summer and fall of 1989 and reported to the CLR Board in November. The second, the Advisory Committee on Library Education, is the successor to the Working Committee. The members, ten library school deans, have been asked to help devise a course of action to accomplish the objectives established by the initial committee.

The substance of the Working Committee report discussed with the CLR Board is as follows.

- Recruit excellent students to librarianship and encourage undergraduate preparation for graduate professional education.

Committee members agreed that it is desirable that a larger number of library school students come to professional education soon after completing their undergraduate education. A special effort is needed to interest promising individuals in the profession as early as possible. There is also general agreement that more attention should be given to undergraduate academic preparation for professional education in three areas:

- a) patterns of thinking (e.g., logic, mathematics)
 - b) tools (e.g., foreign languages, computer applications, statistics)
 - c) subject or functional specialization (art history, rare books, etc.)
- Establish an effective interface between professional education and professional practice.

There are too few purposeful and constructive connections between the professional education system and the profession itself. Creating productive links should, over time, influence in useful ways both the scope and

content of formal education for librarians and the character and capabilities of library staffs. Of immediate interest is exploring the prospects for developing partnerships between library schools and designated teaching libraries. A second area that merits attention is consideration of pre- or postgraduation internships as a means to increase the instructional time available for basic professional education.

Finally, a general review of library staff composition, present and projected, seems required as a way to influence professional education programs and to assure effective use of well-educated professionals.

- Clarify and articulate the content and scope of the scientific core of professional education.

It might be said that, in essence, Information Studies is the academic investigation of how individuals and society make use of accumulated information and the products of research, scholarship, and intellectual creativity. Professional education leads to the understanding and application of the results of such academic investigation. Generally speaking, there has been too little progress in probing in imaginative ways the full range of topics implied in this definition. The lack of fundamental texts, limited understanding of professional functions and responsibilities, and even the diffused content of professional education programs are all evidence of the failure of the profession to come fully to grips with both its obligations and its methods.

- Expand the productivity and influence of faculty research in ways that will assure library schools of full credibility in their university settings.

In general, library schools have a low profile within their universities. Reasons are many—small faculty size, a nontypical student body, large part-time enrollment, and limited prospects for external funding. But perhaps most of all, perceptions that academic programs in library schools are based more on technique than theory and that faculty research is too often modest in quantity and, in some instances, below general academic standards in substance contribute greatly to the limited status of these schools. Since prestige is earned and not bestowed, ways must be found to add strength to faculties and to take the required steps that, over time, will assure the academic credibility of the schools.

With the report of the Working Committee as its starting point, the Advisory Committee on Professional Education began its work in February 1990 and plans to complete its report for CLR by November 1990. Committee discussions and papers prepared by members have identified a number of topics for attention. A partial list includes:

Recruiting

The characteristics of the population of students in accredited U.S. library schools have not changed substantially over the last twenty years.

Broadly speaking, students begin their professional training late (the average age of matriculated students is about 34) and their mobility is limited.

Undergraduate programs in information science

There are good reasons why library schools should consider ways to work with undergraduates, principally to introduce these students to the profession of information studies and to begin to build an understanding of the responsibilities of librarians. Among matters for consideration are preparation for professional education by acquiring necessary abilities and tools—foreign languages, computer skills, logic, mathematics—and the prospect of offering some basic courses of a professional nature as a way to concentrate on advanced courses in graduate training. A third purpose, as pertinent to a liberal education as it is to professional study, is to help undergraduate students understand the promise and problems of living in the “information age.”

Continuing education and schools of library and information science

Continuing education is poorly defined, particularly in relation to continuing training. When continuing education is not offered as part of a structured degree sequence, recognition of accomplishment is uncertain. While there are many problems, it seems evident that, given the demands on the profession in this exceptionally dynamic period, careful attention should be given to the matter. It is certain that, to be effective, continuing education must involve the entire range of professional participants, including librarians themselves, employers, professional societies, library education programs, and accrediting bodies.

Specialization

Despite a long history of concern in the library education community, there is still no normative agreement on what the term “specialization” means at the master’s degree level. Given the limited resources of library and information science education, the ability to provide fully satisfactory specialized programs is a problem that all schools face.

Defining quality

It is essential for the future of professional education that performance be measured in terms of distinction and excellence. How quality will be measured and judged is unclear, but it must be defined as accomplishment well beyond the merely ordinary. Ways must be found to assess purpose, content, faculty, and students against standards of excellence and to judge, over time, the influence of librarianship on teaching and learning.

While these and other topics are receiving attention, the principal task of the Committee is to set in motion a process for accomplishing needed change

in professional education. It is obvious that success will hinge not on statements and proposals but on the intense involvement of purposeful individuals and the energetic participation of schools and their parent institutions, working collaboratively in a common cause.

II. Bibliographic Systems

The Bibliographic Services Study Committee (BSSC) was formed late in 1987 to consider some of the key issues related to bibliographic control and to advise CLR on bibliographic matters. During 1989/90, the committee has concentrated on assessing the pilot phase of the National Coordinated Cataloging Program (NCCP), which has been funded largely by the Council.

The committee's report, *The National Coordinated Cataloging Program: An Assessment of the Pilot Project*, was completed at year's end. Copies are being distributed by CLR to NCCP participants, research libraries, and library schools. The report includes, in addition to the committee's observations concerning the development of NCCP, a research paper, "Economic Aspects of the NCCP Pilot Project"; a review of supplementary data concerning cataloging activity gathered for the use of the committee; the report "A Survey of Copy Cataloging Practices at ARL Libraries"; and the report "Costs and Cost Benefits of Distributed Cataloging to Library of Congress Standards." The several studies combine to add greatly to an understanding of the costs of, and requirements for, cooperative cataloging.

The BSSC members are continuing their work, in cooperation with representatives of the research library community, to stimulate consideration of policy and procedural changes that will optimize cataloging production relative to costs. Toward this end, CLR will consider support for a meeting to review cataloging practices for subdividing subject headings, a matter that has been found to impede cooperative cataloging to a single national standard. The meeting, to be managed by the Library of Congress with BSSC participation, will bring together experts in the field, representatives of national and academic research libraries, and representatives of concerned professional organizations.

III. Communications in Support of Science and Engineering

During the summer of 1989, the National Science Foundation (NSF) asked the Council on Library Resources to explore selected aspects of scientific and engineering communication with the objective of learning more about the relationships between information resources and scientific productivity. Such information is of use in the preparation of the *Science and Engineering Indicators* series of the National Science Board.

The report of this CLR project, which was managed by Dr. Martin Cummings, has been delivered to NSF and copies will be distributed to the research library community during the fall of 1990. The key sections of the report, *Communications in Support of Science and Engineering*, are related to a conference sponsored by CLR that enabled a group of distinguished scientists and academic leaders to consider the general topic. A background paper, the

transactions of the conference, and a summary statement, taken together, suggest many of the pertinent issues and provide a base for future action.

Three additional papers, triggered by the conference discussion, were commissioned by CLR, and two have been completed. The first, by Helen Gee, considers how more might be learned about the information needs and information-seeking methods of scientists and engineers. The second, by Nancy Van House, explores, in a very preliminary way, whether a relationship exists between the extent of library resources and services and the quality and distinction of scientific research in academic settings. A third study, cooperatively developed at Bell Laboratories and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, will compare the investment made for information resources in a small set of academic science libraries with that made for comparable purposes in industrial libraries.

In recent years, CLR has made a number of grants and sponsored many meetings with the purpose of learning more about information needs in all fields and promoting among faculty, librarians, and university officers the kind of open discussion that is essential to long-range planning for information services. While the concerns of scholars working in humanistic and historical disciplines differ in many ways from those of scientists, there are many similarities affecting their respective information settings. For both groups, the same forces are at work: ever-increasing costs, the rapid development of information technologies, and the sheer quantity of information that must be absorbed into the system. In the context of library operations, the principal differences between science and the humanities are the degree of dependence on current, versus historical, information and the requirement for speed of access. Even so, some areas of science need reliable access to both the historical record and the most current information available. The sciences, by their nature, need to have their information base analyzed in great detail, but, increasingly, humanists are looking for comparable attention to their body of literature, which is much larger. Further complicating matters is the requirement to meet various needs for scientific and technical information—for research, obviously, but also for many commercial and industrial enterprises, for teaching at all levels, and for the general public, broadly defined.

All this is to say that the search for signs of scientific progress in the information structure is difficult. It is given that current science is based on information and that the product of science is new information. It seems reasonable to assume that the effectiveness of the information "system" affects the performance of science itself. In turn, shaping the ideal system and measuring its effectiveness in absolute terms is probably an impossible assignment, especially now, when definitions of "ideal" are largely personal and almost all system components are in a state of flux.

But even given the difficulty of understanding the relationship between information resources and research productivity, its study seems worthwhile and carries the promise of improvement that comes with understanding. From what we have learned during the past year, there are three basic aspects

of this general inquiry that merit much more thoughtful and imaginative attention. By their nature, they require more than routine analysis.

1. *The future form of scientific publishing*

How will the growing trend to integrate the information structure with the research process affect the traditional system of scientific publication? Publication in established journals still provides the authenticated historical record for science. However, escalating costs, the uncontrolled national and international commercialization of scientific publishing, and the sheer quantity of material offered for inclusion put the system—which is based on the assumption of wide distribution—seriously at risk. Given the capabilities of information technology, the realities of funding, the need to protect the authenticity of scientific information, and the requirement for unconstrained access, what should be the future form of scientific publishing?

2. *The characteristics of and requirements for scientific communication*

There are various forms of scientific communication, some essentially personal, others affected to various degrees by external conditions. Computer, telecommunications, and information storage technologies have greatly expanded the options for communication among researchers. Too little is known about the needs of scientists and engineers for information, about methods of information transfer related to research needs, and about differences in working patterns and what determines those differences. Further, a better understanding of the relationship between the form and characteristics of information and the utility of such information is essential to the design of future information services. Special care not to assume homogeneity of need is essential in any investigation.

3. *The future form of library services and information systems for science*

Research libraries are being redefined. Rather than being simply buildings, collections, and staff, they are becoming organizations that are intricately linked to each other for purposes of identifying, locating, and providing information in all forms—publications, images, sound, and data. They have made great strides in applying information technology to operations, they are increasingly interdependent in building and maintaining collections, and they have staffs that are more diverse than ever, with technological skills, subject knowledge, and management abilities all represented.

However, the process of making fundamental change, given operating realities and still-valid traditional responsibilities, is difficult. Success will depend in large part on constructive collaboration with user communities. A purposeful and long-term effort to recast library services for the sciences is necessary. The need for a National Library for Science, as one element in a system to assure a comprehensive information service, is one matter requiring exploration. To this end,

the function, structure, and organization of a new national library or service (perhaps one that brings together in some effective combination the Library of Congress and other key science libraries) should be described, paying special attention to the relationship with academic research libraries, prospects for institutional cost containment, and service enhancement for science.

These three topics seem to us to be the key matters for further attention if we are not only to understand how science information and science itself interact, but to make certain that the interaction is as efficient and as productive as possible.

IV. Considering the Future of Academic Research Libraries

In 1986 CLR began a focused effort to promote consideration of the future form of research libraries. More than thirty grants have been made to explore a wide range of topics and issues, from research into specific operating questions to demonstrations of institutional planning for information resources and services. The program is still active but will probably be brought to an end as a discrete CLR activity by the end of 1990/91, although the objectives will necessarily remain a driving force for all Council activities. A full report on the program for the years 1986-1990 is in preparation.

Projects related to planning at the University of California at Los Angeles, the University of Minnesota, and the University of Illinois at Chicago have all been completed. Funded studies include, by way of example, the structure of electronic text, the information needs of philosophers, the information-seeking behavior of a specific set of scientists, the cost of serials, the administrative issues related to the delivery of information in electronic format, and the perceptions of library services held by academic administrators. The diversity of topics and great differences in their scale imply severe difficulty in developing productive discussion, much less constructive action. However, in the course of several formal conferences sponsored by the Council, it became clear that the future of research libraries is in fact getting attention, constructive changes are taking place, and there are many talented people exercising both leadership and good judgment.

Based on what has been learned, and convinced that purposeful planning for information resources and services is essential to the well-being of every research university, CLR has developed a special program offering grants of \$100,000 to as many as five universities in partial support of institutional policy studies and implementation planning for future library resources and services. It is anticipated that these awards will be made by December 30, 1990.

One of the most important aspects of the research program has been the participation of faculty and university officers. The most extensive discussions were those of the Research Library Committee, which was established by the Council on Library Resources to explore the future form of the academic research library, with special concentration on the interests and needs of faculty members in the humanities and social sciences. Committee member-

ship includes university presidents, senior academic officers, faculty members, and librarians and archivists, reflecting the cosponsorship of the committee by the American Council of Learned Societies, the Association of American Universities, and the Social Science Research Council.

The full committee met five times during 1988 and 1989 and explored many topics. Presentations by experts in areas of special interest and several sponsored meetings of scholars on topics pertinent to the committee's agenda also helped to inform the committee. During a final three-day session in December 1989, members reviewed past discussions and then concentrated on the key issues incorporated in a statement that was widely distributed in May 1990. The full text is reproduced here for the record.

A Statement from the Research Library Committee

sponsored by

American Council of Learned Societies

Association of American Universities

Council on Library Resources

Social Science Research Council

In Brief

The information base for teaching and learning is being rapidly transformed by integrated information technologies—computers, telecommunications, and text storage systems. Rising costs and the compounding of information quantity amplify the problem.

Libraries, long responsible for assembling and maintaining that base, have made good use of technology for internal operations, but how libraries and faculties will deal with digitized information and unbounded means of access is not determined. It is uncertain whether universities and their libraries will productively embrace information-age capabilities or be engulfed by them.

The research library must be redefined. To set specifications for the new capabilities while protecting the substance of the old, several key steps and many specific actions are needed. To begin the process:

- Each university must undertake a fundamental rethinking of library and information service objectives.
- The organizational and financial capabilities to accomplish institutional expectations for library services must be specified and met.
- Faculty and librarians should join forces to set realistic, forward-looking national objectives for the resources and services required for research and should actively promote productive collaboration between principal research libraries and the Library of Congress.
- Librarians must view their responsibilities expansively. The core of their profession is as much educational as it is technical, and they need to bring both academic and managerial capabilities to bear on the important and increasingly complex matter of putting information to use.

The Challenge to Research Libraries

Higher education is in a period of questioning, reflection, and change. While the importance of universities is widely understood and their work endorsed, they are, nevertheless, now more than ever before in competition for financial support with other, equally essential, public enterprises. The audience universities serve is increasingly diverse and brings additional requirements, more attention to teaching is being strongly urged, and the pertinence of what is taught is being scrutinized carefully because there is persistent concern about the purpose and results of undergraduate education. Further, the dependence of teaching and research on computer and related technologies has grown rapidly and has added a new level of structural complexity to continuing operations. Staffing problems loom large, and it is assumed many universities will have to take heroic measures during the next decade to cope with anticipated faculty retirements, especially in humanistic and historical disciplines.

Each of these forces has economic implications, and because financial resources will continue to be limited, the years ahead will require refinement of purpose and invention in method. Choices will have to be made and new ways of accomplishing university objectives will have to be found.

What is true for universities is true for their libraries, where obligations to the past, present, and future have converged with great force. Large portions of accumulated collections are physically fragile; current publication volume is expanding worldwide, and expectations of users are honed by what they now see as technically possible. More fundamentally, it is not clear that the research library of today can be a paradigm for the twenty-first-century library. The rise of new fields of inquiry and the shifting organization of knowledge into new configurations present a demanding challenge for libraries, which conduct their collecting and bibliographic work on a historically established base. Further, uncertainty about organization and operations is implicit in a future where the extent and influence of innovation in telecommunications and electronic publishing are essentially unknown.

The form of future library service will be shaped by how well librarians cope with the sheer quantity of published material, the growing number of print and nonprint formats used to store information of interest, escalating requirements of users for access to everything of importance, new and rising costs, and the structural changes in the system of scholarly communication brought on by the interrelated technologies that are transforming how information is stored, organized, processed, and transmitted.

Fortunately, librarians have a strong record of accomplishment. They have cooperatively developed computerized bibliographic systems that identify and locate millions of publications. They have pioneered in the application to library operations and services of an ever-increasing array of information technologies. Most important, they have demonstrated that they can join forces to attack, on a national level, such intractable problems as preservation.

The years ahead will be demanding ones, but the foundation on which to build is largely in place. The members of the Research Library Committee recognize the difficulties libraries face, but also see an exceptional opportunity to make constructive change and assure for academic research libraries, individually and collectively, their unique, educationally important role into the twenty-first century.

The Central Issues for Research Libraries

For libraries to succeed in a much-changed setting, the policies and priorities of each university relating to library resources and services need to be explored fully and set. Of equal importance, the capabilities required to follow those policies need to be identified and provided.

Many issues requiring attention were identified by RLC members. These examples suggest the range of pertinent policy questions.

- How can the university determine and maintain a proper balance in library support of the various scholarly disciplines that may require different services?
- What are realistic expectations for, and limits to, interinstitutional cooperation in such areas as developing complementary collections, lending materials, sharing storage space, and preserving historical collections?
- How can librarians and scholars, working in close collaboration institutionally and nationally, promote the development of additional specialized collections and the penetrating bibliographic analysis required by multi-disciplinary research?
- How should the university manage access to and funding for electronic texts and information services that are charged on a per-use basis rather than sold outright? Should such charges be passed through to users, as long-distance telephone and other priced services often are?
- How far beyond conventional print materials should the library's responsibility extend, particularly in electronically stored information?
- How should the university deal with the space requirements for storage of the ever-increasing volume of printed scholarly materials?
- What should be the instructional role of libraries?

Policy issues need to be addressed specifically and regularly in each university. Faculty, librarians, and administrative officers must all take part in the process. Librarians have the responsibility to bring the issues to the table and press for a response, but they should not be expected to set policy in isolation.

Recommendations

Policy guidance, while essential, is not enough. The capabilities required to act must also be in place. While many specific points were made during RLC deliberations, they can be gathered under a few principal heads.

The Library of Congress

The relationship of the Library of Congress (LC) to other "national"

collections must be carefully reexamined. A means to assess periodically the needs and performance of that relationship should be created, with special attention to the state of the nation's resources and services for research.

For research librarians and for scholars working in humanistic and historical fields, the Library of Congress is an institution of great importance. The many bibliographic services, especially LC bibliographic records, serve as the national standard. The special formats of material, such as maps and recordings, that are comprehensively collected and cataloged add substantially to the national pool. The LC collections range widely and deeply into almost all areas of interest to researchers, and again, the comprehensive inclusion of special materials—prints, photographs, music, manuscripts—that complement printed works make the library a national treasure for scholars.

But even given the distinction of the Library of Congress, from the scholar's point of view the *de facto* national library for humanistic and historical scholarship is the aggregate of the Library of Congress and the other academic and independent research libraries with distinctive collections. This small group of libraries, collectively, contains scholarly resources that are unmatched in any country of the world. However, there is too little true collaboration among them and with the Library of Congress to assure that the full benefits those resources offer are realized and their comprehensiveness maintained.

Change in every aspect of our national information structure and the importance of such change to the national well-being calls for broad and consistent public attention to the quality of the nation's research base. Scholars, the directors of principal research libraries, and the Library of Congress need to join forces and plot the course for a fully productive alliance.

Commitment to collaboration

Historically, research libraries collected and acted in isolation from each other. Individuals visited libraries to make use of available collections and went elsewhere for what they did not find. During the past fifty years, research libraries have sought to respond to what have become essentially unconstrained interests of faculty and the ever-expanding agenda of higher education. Collections became global in coverage, the categories of publications acquired increased, and, still, user expectations have consistently kept ahead of collecting efforts.

The sheer quantity of material has made self-sufficiency an unrealistic aspiration. In both collecting and building the bibliographic base, interdependence is now an acknowledged, but not necessarily fully embraced, principle. Underscoring the fact, telecommunications capabilities have expanded dramatically and changed forever the relationship among libraries and between libraries, their users, and the producers of information.

While a far-distant future may hold the prospect that some combination of perfectly integrated technologies will make all information personally accessible (the ultimate form of academic independence), the reality is that all of

the forces at work—e.g., the rapidly growing quantity of information sources, the increasing complexity of demand, the volatility of technology, and the obvious presence of escalating costs inherent in any dynamic setting—make it essential that there be an aggressive commitment to effective collaboration. Improving the capacity to shape and use cooperative enterprises deserves full administrative attention. Here, perhaps more than in any other university effort, innovation in organization, appropriate financing, and assessment of performance is required.

Research libraries and scholarly communication

Scholarly Communication, the report of the ACLS-sponsored National Enquiry, clearly and forcefully describes scholarly communication as a system of interdependent elements—the interests and work of individual scholars, the disciplines, research libraries, the book and journal publishing communities, and public and private funding sources. Action (or inaction) in one element inevitably affects all others. This message of ten years ago is still valid and is still insufficiently attended to. It is essential, in the light of the great changes now under way in each system component, that the scholarly community take the lead in assessing the impact of actual and projected change on system performance and in making visible both negative and positive results. Changes made anywhere in the system, including in the practices of scholars themselves, need to be scrutinized regularly. Promising trends need to be encouraged; disturbing ones should quickly be explored and, if truly threatening, forcefully identified. Communication among scholars, across disciplines, and between the world of scholarship and society at large must be unconstrained and effective. The scholarly world, both for its own well-being and for the public benefit, must be the system monitor.

The library in the university structure

The scope of library responsibilities reaches across all academic levels and affects all fields of study. Research libraries, by their nature, not only respond to individual users; they also influence what users do. The work of universities is inseparable from the substance of libraries, and the continuity inherent in the scholarly enterprise is reflected in every aspect of library operations. Libraries can be active contributors to the work of universities, but only if librarians are constructively involved in the development of academic programs. It is essential that the library be linked effectively to the faculty and the academic and administrative leadership of the university and that each of those university sectors does what is required to make the process work.

The library staff

The university community obviously expects that library management will be responsible, imaginative, and productive. Collections must be built and maintained, needs of users met, and operating capabilities constantly refined to contain costs and assure that future as well as present interests are served.

But universities should expect a great deal more than managerial competence. Librarians are each university's information service specialists. Of

necessity, all librarians should be well informed about the issues of the information age—the structures for publication and distribution, information economics, government information policy, direct and indirect constraints on access to information, and the influence of information technologies. Some must have a sound understanding of the capabilities and prospects for the technologies pertinent to scholarly communication and library operations, not simply the techniques of use. Many staff members must have an active interest in a subject area, because a professional staff with strong academic credentials and a visible academic presence can greatly extend the range and influence of library service. Further, at least some staff members should be capable teachers, not only of the techniques of library use but of the substance of their calling, helping students to understand the information setting in which they will live and work.

While scholarship and the nation's information structure are inseparable, an understanding of how that structure works and its effect on research and teaching is not yet well developed. Broad-gauged, interdisciplinary research in information studies is required, and librarians have an obligation to encourage such work. As those in the academic enterprise most knowledgeable about the organization and management of information, librarians need to contribute to the analytical work that is required for a better understanding of how information is generated and used. Librarians need also to work with the growing number of scholars who are adopting information technologies for their research, both to assure that library systems enhance such scholarship and to assure that research results can be productively integrated into library information services.

The factors that affect the flow of information within disciplines, among institutions, through society, and across borders must be identified and their importance to the educational enterprise understood. The ultimate responsibilities of the profession are to control information system complexity, to maintain information authenticity, to assure equitable access to information, and to promote effective use, by all components of society, of that which has been learned.

Funding

The budgets of research libraries are always complex and often incomplete—complex because they reflect a continuing capital investment in building and maintaining a research collection as well as the costs of current service and instructional support, and incomplete because, in most cases, such items as space costs and certain components of institutional overhead are seldom included. Funding is further complicated by the need to invest in the information technology now required with no clear sense of the magnitude of continuing costs, and by the growing number of costly commercial information services being offered to libraries and their users.

Library costs need to be more carefully dissected and better understood in order that the value of past investment in collections not be unduly jeopard-

dized and to insure that the fiscal implications of innovation are fully understood. Policies and costs must be more carefully related to each other, and the long-term financial implications of policy decisions need to be fully described.

The capabilities of the information age cannot be viewed simply as an extrapolation of what has gone before. They are essentially additive, and the new costs as well as current funding realities suggest that some subtractions from established operating patterns will be required to keep accounts in balance.

A Final Note

The Research Library Committee has been able to underscore the importance of its assignment, it has identified issues that need attention, and it has speculated about the implications of alternative courses of action. It cannot by itself, however, take effective action. Given a topic as complex and diffuse as the future form of research libraries and the information structure underlying teaching and scholarship in humanistic and historical studies, action will have to come in many places and over a period of time.

This statement reaches the obvious but not always recognized conclusion that each university should put in place a continuing capability to set and make known its particular specifications for library resources and services. For such an important matter, an institutional touchstone is required to help keep expectations realistic, to guide the administration of libraries, and to provide a base for assessing the costs, values, and service implications of offerings from the growing number of information vendors seeking a market for their wares.

Beyond the large array of immediate questions, there are other topics of great interest needing attention. The economics of information, information ownership, the influence of technology on access to information, public information policy (both national and international), and factors affecting information utility are only examples. The discussions of the Research Library Committee mark the beginning of a new effort to deal with one of the most important and complex subjects of our time, but it is certain that the discussion must be a continuing one if the voice of the academic world is to be heard by those shaping the information age.

CLR Grants and Contracts, 1989/1990

I. Library Operations and Planning

The Council sponsors a wide-ranging program of research and analysis concerning all aspects of library operations. Its primary aim is to consider the future form of research libraries. In practice, this has meant making grants in the following areas:

1. Research

The research program concentrates on strategic planning and management issues in research libraries, broadly defined. As the grants that follow show, funded proposals in this program area range from a consideration of the ethical standards for rare book librarians to an analysis of the information needs of scientists and engineers. The disparate proposals recorded here share, however, the common goal of providing better and more efficient service to the users of research libraries.

American Council of Learned Societies

For partial support of the United States participants attending the "Conference on Scholarship and Technology in the Humanities," May 1990, sponsored by the British Library.

American Library Association

To the Rare Books and Manuscripts Section of the Association of College and Research Libraries to support a revision of the 1987 "Standards for Ethical Conduct for Rare Book, Manuscript, and Special Collections Librarians." Principal Investigator: Beverly P. Lynch, Ethical Standards Review Committee.

Helen H. Gee, Consultant

A contract to prepare a report on the information needs and information-seeking practices of scientists, and to suggest a research process for further analysis of information-seeking habits and the relationship of information services to research activity and productivity.

Harvard University

To hold a conference entitled "Research Trends and Library Resources" in February 1990. The aim of the conference was to identify new or changing tendencies in research in the humanities and social sciences that may have implications for libraries in their efforts to acquire and provide access to research materials. Principal Investigator: Lawrence Dowler, Harvard College Library.

Massachusetts Institute of Technology

To support a cooperative research project entitled "Retrieving and Analyzing Published Literature as a Tool for Understanding Technological Development." Recipients: Michael A. Rappa, Sloan School of Management, MIT; Susan N. Bjørner, MIT Libraries; and Raghu Garud, Stern School of Business, New York University.

National Agricultural Library

To develop a training package, "Computer-Assisted Instruction for Cataloging," in cooperation with the University of Wisconsin-Madison and the University of Pittsburgh. This instructional program will draw on hypertext and graphics capabilities to instruct novice catalogers in the basics of descriptive cataloging and related bibliographic concepts. Principal Investigator: Sarah E. Thomas, NAL.

Northwestern University

A cooperative research grant to develop expert system and hypertext training programs for part-time student library assistants. Recipients: Lloyd A. Davidson, Seeley G. Mudd Library, and Gilbert K. Krulee, Department of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science.

University of California at Los Angeles

To investigate the procedural rules by which reference librarians make decisions, and the impact this knowledge has on the teaching of reference and the quality of reference services rendered. Principal Investigator: John Richardson, Jr., Graduate School of Library and Information Science.

University of Colorado-Boulder

For a case study of the information-seeking behavior of the scientists and graduate students of the Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research. Recipient: Martha Andrews, Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research.

University of Illinois

For a study of database searching on CD-ROM, comparing the results of end-user searching with results from two modes of searching by skilled intermediaries. Principal Investigator: F. W. Lancaster, Graduate School of Library and Information Science.

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

To study the process of organizational review in libraries by examining cases of structural change in selected library organizations and assessing various change process models. The goal of this study is to develop guidelines for applying such models to other organizational settings. Recipient: Joe A. Hewitt, Davis Library.

Nancy Van House, University of California at Berkeley

A contract for a study of the relationship between productivity in university-based scientific and engineering research and the level of current support and investment provided for library and information resources.

2. Access Services

Historically, librarians have been charged with the care and preservation of the collections entrusted to them. In modern times, the emphasis has changed to include the assurance of equitable access to all. It is hoped that each of the funded proposals in the Access Services Program will contribute toward this end.

Martha Brogan, Yale University

In partial support of travel expenses incurred to produce the manuscript *Research Guide to Libraries and Archives in the Low Countries*.

Marianna Tax Choldin, University of Illinois

Support for a study of the Soviet practice of censoring via translation during the period from the Bolshevik revolution through the present era and examination of the role of libraries in providing (and obstructing) access to foreign publications.

Cornell University

In support of research into the horticultural literature from 1850 to 1950 to produce a core list of historical monographs still valuable in teaching and research. Recipient: Mary Van Buren, New York State Agricultural Experiment Station.

Kent State University

To support a cooperative research project entitled "Fostering Information Literate Students at a Medium-Sized Research Library: A Comparison of Manual and Online Searches on an Interdisciplinary Topic." Recipients: Laura Bartolo and Barbara Schloman, University Libraries, and Tim Smith, School of Journalism.

The Library of Congress

For a conference to establish short- and long-term policies governing bibliographic records for variant formats of the same item. Principal Investigator: Henriette D. Avram, Collections Services.

Pennsylvania State University

To study the searching behavior of remote access users of online public access catalogs. The goal of this study is to generate recommendations for OPAC enhancements to improve the remote interface, and for support services that will better assist remote access users. Recipient: Sally W. Kalin, Pennsylvania State University Libraries.

University of Alabama

A cooperative research grant to conduct a pilot study to assess the need for, feasibility of, and characteristics of an online bibliographical reference database on the subject of simulation/gaming. Recipients: David Crookall, Department of English, and Larry Harbin, University Libraries.

3. Cataloging and Bibliographic Services

A key element in providing equitable access is the national and international structure of cataloging systems and bibliographic services. In the modern world of computers and telecommunications, bibliographic services have become increasingly important by providing comprehensive coverage of and rapid access to published materials. The projects noted here were selected with an eye toward increasing the efficiency of this critical function.

American Library Association

To the Catalog Use Committee of the ALA Reference and Adult Services Division for a think tank on the "Present and Future of the Online Catalog." Principal Investigator: Suzanne K. Lorimer, Catalog Use Committee.

University of Toronto

A cooperative research grant to investigate the feasibility of using conceptually based computer tutorials to train students to use online catalogs. Recipients: Joan Cherry, Faculty of Library and Information Science, and Marshall Clinton, University of Toronto Library.

4. Library Collections and Preservation

Preservation of the historical record is the *raison d'être* of academic and research libraries. Without a well-cared-for collection, all other library activities are for naught. Large, deteriorating, older collections and fragile modern media have made preservation an immensely complicated and expensive proposition in the United States alone. The difficulty is even more immense when considered from an international point of view. The proposals selected for funding in this program area will help address this serious and ever-growing problem.

Association of the Bar of the City of New York

To help prepare and produce materials needed in a campaign to raise funds for the preservation of the New York State Records on Appeal. Principal Investigator: Kurt Struver, Development Counsel.

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

To continue the Committee on Institutional Cooperation's task force on mass deacidification by exploring important operational, materials handling, and budgetary issues.

II. Librarianship

For many years, the Council has taken as one of its charges the support of exceptional librarians at every stage of their careers. It has fulfilled this charge through a variety of programs, including the Academic Library Management Intern Program, the CLR Fellows Program, and the Cooperative Research Program. Many of the grants listed in this report are drawn from the latter two programs. They are designed to assist librarians who wish to do research connected to library operations and services, or other professional projects of importance, either alone or in concert with other librarians or academic faculty members. In addition, CLR has funded several projects undertaken by library schools to provide specialized education opportunities for practicing librarians. The goal of all these programs is to provide continuing education assistance to the individuals who are responsible for the operation of the complex and costly information structure that undergirds research and scholarship.

John Buschman, Rider College; Jeffrey Alan Douglas, Knox College; and Jocelyn Sheppard, Bethany College

Support to attend the American Antiquarian Society seminar entitled "The American Renaissance: Critical and Bibliographical Perspectives," June 1990.

Ferris State University

Partial support to complete a manuscript entitled *Ladders Across Culture: Instructional Media, Books, and Libraries in the Catholic Mission to Oregon, 1835-1885*. Recipient: Lawrence J. McCrank, Library and Instructional Services.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)

Funding for a second class of Robert Vosper IFLA Fellows, a program named for a distinguished American librarian, which is intended to stimulate interest in international aspects of librarianship.

Purdue University

To complete research on the career of Azariah Smith Root, the director of the Oberlin Library from 1887 to 1927, to result in a monograph entitled *Azariah Smith Root and the American College Library*. Recipient: Mark Tucker, Humanities, Social Science, and Education Library.

Simmons College

To conduct a field test of the Library of Congress's *Training the Trainer* course. The aim of this project is to test the usefulness of the course's materials and approach for academic libraries in general. Principal Investigator: Sheila S. Intner, Graduate School of Library and Information Science.

University of Illinois

For a summer institute entitled "Advancing Research on the Library in Transition." The institute brought together selected librarians with institute and library school faculty to discuss theoretical and methodological issues and to present their ongoing research. Principal Investigator: Leigh Estabrook, Graduate School of Library and Information Science.

University of Michigan

To initiate a Joint Research and Education Program with the School of Information and Library Studies and the University Library. These units will offer broad-based courses on information issues to undergraduate and selected graduate students. Principal Investigator: Robert M. Warner, School of Information and Library Studies.

University of Oklahoma

A cooperative research grant for a survey of the career development patterns of academic librarians in Oklahoma; the responses will be compared with fifteen years of national data. Recipients: Michael Havener and Robert D. Swisher, School of Library and Information Studies, and Wilbur Stolt, Library Public Services.

University of Redlands

For a historical study of the impact of selected technologies on the development of libraries, especially as agents of change in the social and organizational structure of libraries. Recipient: Klaus Musmann, Armacost Library.

University of Rhode Island

To undertake a survey of library school faculty to project future needs for replacement faculty. Principal Investigator: Elizabeth Futas, Graduate School of Library and Information Studies.

University of South Carolina

For a study entitled "Knowledge and Skills for Health Information Professionals" aimed at increasing the effectiveness of health science librarians. Principal Investigator: Fred W. Roper, College of Library and Information Science.

Program Committees and Project Participants

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Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to library service and information systems, with the primary objective of improving the quality and performance of academic and research libraries. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the broad areas of the Council's program, as described in this report. In addition, the Council sponsors several competitive programs, including the CLR Fellows program, the Cooperative Research program, and the Academic Library Management Intern Program. These programs are described in brochures available from CLR.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the proposed work, indicate methodology, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide an estimate of total costs and funding requirements. CLR will respond promptly with an indication of interest. If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested.

Full documentation should include:

1. A concise description of the proposed project.
2. A thorough explanation of the work to be done, including objectives and methods to be employed. A timetable, pertinent background information, and plans for evaluation of results should also be provided.
3. A detailed budget linking costs to project components.
4. Curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

Proposals are carefully reviewed by CLR staff and, when necessary, external advisors, who consider such matters as relevance to current CLR interests and activities; relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work described; and importance of anticipated results. The Council also looks for evidence of institutional support, including cost sharing. With

the exception of a few cyclical programs, there are no submission deadlines.

Support is not provided for construction or renovation, collection acquisitions, routine operating costs, activities judged to be of limited influence, or work that essentially repeats previous research. CLR does not fund indirect costs or, with rare exceptions, equipment purchases. While CLR, in consultation with its advisors, often initiates and promotes work in program areas, exploratory correspondence and conversation are always welcome, and all proposals receive careful consideration.

All inquiries should be addressed to Council on Library Resources, 1785 Massachusetts Avenue, N.W., Suite 313, Washington, D.C. 20036.

Administrative Notes

The administrative actions taken during the year 1989-90 include the following:

1. Eleanor Sacks, who served a one-year appointment as program associate, has returned to Portland, Oregon. Her position has been assumed by Caroline Mitchell. Ms. Mitchell is a graduate of the University of Michigan and the Yale School of Organization and Management and is currently a part-time student at the Catholic University School of Library and Information Science.
Susan Adams has joined the Council staff as Controller. Ms. Adams, a graduate of the University of Pittsburgh, succeeded Linda Hutter on February 7, 1990.
2. Because the staff of the Council is small, special efforts are made to assure that all proposals to the Council get full review, both internally and by outside experts. To supplement CLR program staff, a proposal review committee was established and met monthly during the year to consider proposals submitted to CLR. Members of the committee for 1989-90 are listed on page 32. A comparable committee will be formed for 1990-91.
3. An additional foundation was added to the list of CLR supporters when the W. K. Kellogg Foundation made a grant to CLR in the amount of \$200,000. The Kellogg funds are earmarked principally for CLR activities in the field of continuing professional education and for exploratory studies in library education generally.
4. The Council's Board has established a Search Committee to identify candidates to succeed the current president on his retirement. Members include William N. Hubbard, Jr., M.D. (Chairman); Patricia Battin; Charles Churchwell; Billy Frye; and Maximilian Kempner.
5. The Council has continued its contract to provide support services to the Commission on Preservation and Access through FY 1990-91.
6. With the approval of the CLR Board, the accounting firm of Coopers & Lybrand was selected for the annual audit of the financial records of CLR.

7. The following foundations were among the supporters of Council activities during 1989/1990. All deserve the thanks of the library community.

The J. Paul Getty Trust
The W. K. Kellogg Foundation
The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
The National Science Foundation
The Pew Charitable Trusts

ACTIVE PROJECTS

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Grants and Contracts Active in Fiscal 1990 (unaudited)

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
American Council of Learned Societies				
New York, N.Y.				
International conference on humanistic scholarship and technology	\$ -0-	\$ 10,000	\$ 10,000	\$ -0-
American Library Association				
Chicago, Ill.				
Standards for ethical conduct for rare book, manuscript, and special collections librarians	-0-	5,000	-0-	5,000
Think tank on the uses of online catalogs	-0-	1,775	-0-	1,775
Association of the Bar of the City of New York, Inc.				
New York, N.Y.				
Preservation of records on appeal	-0-	10,000	10,000	-0-
Trudi Bellardo				
Washington, D.C.				
History of online information retrieval systems	100	-0-	-0-	100
The Bridge to China Foundation				
Oakland, Calif.				
Book drive for Chinese universities	4,516	-0-	4,516	-0-
Brigham Young University				
Provo, Utah				
Prototype of a non-damaging book return unit	7,500	-0-	5,000	2,500

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
Martha L. Brogan				
New Haven, Conn.				
Research Guide to Libraries and Archives in the Low Countries	-0-	500	500	-0-
John Buschman				
Allentown, Pa.				
American Antiquarian Society/ Council on Library Resources fellowship	-0-	627	627	-0-
Marianna Tax Choldin				
Urbana, Ill.				
Study of Soviet practice of censoring via translation	5,060	800	5,860	-0-
Columbia University				
New York, N.Y.				
Measuring the public services impact of an online catalog	11,200	-0-	-0-	11,200
Commission on Preservation and Access				
Washington, D.C.				
General support	150,000	-0-	16,667	133,333
Cornell University				
Geneva, N.Y.				
Core literature research in horticulture from 1850-1950	-0-	6,300	5,800	500
Jeffrey Alan Douglas				
Galesburg, Ill.				
American Antiquarian Society/ Council on Library Resources fellowship	-0-	475	-0-	475
European Foundation for Library Cooperation				
Brussels, Belgium				
General support	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
Ferris State University				
Big Rapids, Mich.				
Study of books and libraries in the Pacific Northwest territory, 1835-85	-0-	600	600	-0-
Franklin & Marshall College				
Lancaster, Pa.				
Preservation and collection management at liberal arts college libraries	2,980	-0-	2,500	480
Helen H. Gee				
Potomac, Md.				
Information seeking practices of research scientists	-0-	12,000	12,000	-0-
Harvard University				
Cambridge, Mass.				
Conference on research trends and library resources	-0-	7,500	7,000	500
Study of electronic information delivery	16,250	(16,250)	-0-	-0-
Symposium on music librarianship in America	2,000	-0-	2,000	-0-
Indiana University of Pennsylvania				
Indiana, Pa.				
Improving subject access in online public access catalogs	25,000	-0-	20,000	5,000
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions				
The Hague, Netherlands				
IFLA Fellows program -				
1989-92	80,000	(40,000)	-0-	40,000
1990-91	-0-	40,000	-0-	40,000

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
Johns Hopkins University				
Baltimore, Md.				
Knowledge management: expanding the scholarly role of research libraries	182,808	-0-	50,000	132,808
Kent State University				
Kent, Ohio				
Comparison of online and manual search capabilities of students	-0-	1,000	-0-	1,000
Library of Congress				
Washington, D.C.				
Conference on multiple version issues	-0-	22,650 (22,650)	-0-	-0-
Evaluation of the Cataloging in Publication Program	-0-	25,000 (25,000)	-0-	-0-
Massachusetts Institute of Technology				
Cambridge, Mass.				
Retrieving and analyzing published literature	-0-	2,600	2,600	-0-
Museum Computer Network				
Syracuse, N. Y.				
Testing the use of MARC formats for cataloging art objects	5,000	(402)	4,598	-0-
National Agricultural Library				
Beltsville, Md.				
Development of a computer-assisted instructional program for cataloging	-0-	50,084	25,000	25,084
National Commission on Libraries and Information Science				
Washington, D.C.				
Invitational conference on information literacy	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
National Information Standards				
Organization				
Gaithersburg, Md.				
Development of an American national standard for hardcover edition bindings	20,700	(15,000)	1,164	4,536
U.S. representation at an international meeting on paper permanence	2,000	(774)	1,226	-0-
Northwestern University				
Evanston, Ill.				
Expert systems for job training and support	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
OCLC Online Computer Library Center				
Dublin, Ohio				
Increase accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	3,700	-0-	-0-	3,700
Pennsylvania State University				
University Park, Pa.				
Remote access use of library online public access catalogs	-0-	1,031	1,031	-0-
Purdue University				
West Lafayette, Ind.				
Career of Azariah Smith Root at Oberlin College	-0-	750	750	-0-
Rutgers University				
New Brunswick, N.J.				
Impact of interdisciplinary research on library collection building	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
Jocelyn Sheppard				
Washington, Pa.				
American Antiquarian Society/ Council on Library Resources fellowship	-0-	627	-0-	627

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
Simmons College				
Boston, Mass.				
Field test of the Library of Congress's "Training the Trainer" Course	-0-	6,449	5,500	949
Symposium on solutions to the problems of recruiting, educating and training cataloging librarians	1,300	-0-	-0-	1,300
Stanford University				
Stanford, Calif.				
Economic analysis of scholarly periodical costs	27,800	-0-	25,000	2,800
Syracuse University				
Syracuse, N.Y.				
Textual analysis of information needs derived from abstracts of documents	1,913	-0-	1,913	-0-
University of Alabama				
Tuscaloosa, Ala.				
Book on library education	5,800	-0-	3,500	2,300
Pilot study for an online bibliographical reference database for simulation/gaming	2,986	-0-	2,986	-0-
University of Alberta				
Edmonton, Alberta, Canada				
Program design for regional resource sharing	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
University of California				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Elucidation and validation of the knowledge used by reference librarians	-0-	14,330	13,000	1,330
Research program: long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in research universities	169,141	-0-	21,717	147,424
Senior fellows conference - 1988	5,000	(11,430)	(6,430)	-0-
Senior fellows program - 1989	30,000	(3,171)	26,829	-0-
Study of microcomputer-based digital imaging as a technique for preservation of library materials	2,500	(17,604)	(15,104)	-0-
University of Colorado				
Boulder, Colo.				
Information-seeking behavior of scientists	-0-	5,150	4,550	600
University of Georgia				
Athens, Ga.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	36,508	(31,628)	4,880	-0-
University of Illinois				
Urbana, Ill.				
Advanced research institute	-0-	24,007	22,000	2,007
CIC task force on mass deacidification	-0-	6,000	-0-	6,000
Study of searching strategies on CD-ROM	-0-	32,512	15,000	17,512
Developing and evaluating online catalog interface enhancements	2,000	-0-	-0-	2,000

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
University of Kentucky				
Lexington, Ky.				
Revision of the <i>Guide to the Library of Congress Classification</i>	3,000	-0-	2,000	1,000
University of Maryland				
College Park, Md.				
Anglo-American cataloging rules as a knowledge base	613	(69)	544	-0-
University of Michigan				
Ann Arbor, Mich.				
Increase accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	2,925	(85)	2,840	-0-
Joint education and research program	-0-	25,000	20,000	5,000
Second European Conference on Archives	5,000	-0-	5,000	-0-
University of Missouri				
Columbia, Mo.				
Study of information needs of philosophers	2,625	(539)	2,086	-0-
University of North Carolina				
Chapel Hill, N.C.				
Study of the organizational review process in research libraries	-0-	4,412	4,000	412
University of Oklahoma				
Norman, Okla.				
Career and communication patterns of academic librarians	-0-	2,936	-0-	2,936
University of Pittsburgh				
Pittsburgh, Pa.				
An advanced institute for government archivists	40,676	-0-	15,000	25,676

	FY 1990			
	Unpaid 6/30/89	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/90
University of Redlands				
Redlands, Calif.				
Diffusion of technological innovations in libraries	-0-	7,350	6,850	500
University of Rhode Island				
Kingston, R.I.				
Study of replacement needs for library school faculty	-0-	3,850	3,000	850
University of South Carolina				
Columbia, S.C.				
Study of the knowledge and skills required for health information professionals	-0-	9,830	5,000	4,830
University of Toronto				
Toronto, Ontario, Canada				
Information retrieval systems and their users	40,000	-0-	26,000	14,000
User performance with online catalogs	-0-	2,550	2,550	-0-
University of Wisconsin				
Madison, Wis.				
Measurement and evaluation of library reference service	5,605	(2,359)	4,500 (1,254)	-0-
Nancy Van House				
Berkeley, Calif.				
Study of library resources in the sciences	-0-	14,800 (2,976)	11,824	-0-
Yale University				
New Haven, Conn.				
Training support for the institution of self-managing teams within technical services	2,400	-0-	-0-	2,400
Other refunds and adjustments from prior years' grants and contracts				
	\$ -0-	\$ (28,598)	\$ (28,598)	\$ -0-
Totals	\$914,606	\$361,495 (218,535)	\$458,508 (51,386)	\$ 650,444

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Report of Independent Accountants

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

We have audited the accompanying balance sheet of Council on Library Resources, Inc. (the Council) as of June 30, 1990, and the related statements of revenue, expenses and changes in fund balance, cash flows and functional expenses for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit. The financial statements of the Council as of June 30, 1989, were audited by other auditors, whose report dated August 21, 1989, expressed an unqualified opinion on those statements, from which condensed statements are included for comparative purposes only.

We conducted our audit in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of Council on Library Resources, Inc. as of June 30, 1990, and the results of its operations and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles.

Coopers & Lybrand
Washington, D.C.
August 31, 1990

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Balance Sheet

June 30, 1990

(with comparative totals for 1989)

	<u>1990</u>	<u>Totals</u> <u>1989</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and cash equivalents (Note 2)	\$ 790,269	\$ 457,059
Short-term investments (Note 2)	3,099,468	3,083,300
Grants receivable (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	300,000	900,000
Restricted	409,900	837,160
Other assets (Note 6)	<u>94,529</u>	<u>115,549</u>
Total assets	<u>\$4,694,166</u>	<u>\$5,393,068</u>
 LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Accounts payable and accrued expenses	\$ 38,739	\$ 54,812
Grants and contracts payable (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	205,473	305,836
Restricted	444,971	608,770
Deferred revenue (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	600,000	900,000
Restricted	<u>907,192</u>	<u>1,046,416</u>
Total liabilities	<u>2,196,375</u>	<u>2,915,834</u>
Fund balance—unrestricted	<u>2,497,791</u>	<u>2,477,234</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u>\$4,694,166</u>	<u>\$5,393,068</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statement of Revenue, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

for the year ended June 30, 1990
(with comparative totals for 1989)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Totals</u> <u>1990</u>	<u>Totals</u> <u>1989</u>
Revenue (Note 2):				
Grants and contracts	\$ 300,000	\$349,124	\$ 649,124	\$3,200,177
Contributions	—	—	—	259,578
Interest	324,332	—	324,332	372,975
	<u>624,332</u>	<u>349,124</u>	<u>973,456</u>	<u>3,832,730</u>
Expenses (Notes 2, 3, 4 and 5):				
Program:				
Research	8,000	269,990	277,990	634,464
Access	34,040	2,374	36,414	285,195
Bibliography	55,849	—	55,849	123,434
Librarianship	191,245	76,760	268,005	501,871
Library resources and preservation	21,243	—	21,243	2,262,016
	<u>310,377</u>	<u>349,124</u>	<u>659,501</u>	<u>3,806,980</u>
Total program expenses	310,377	349,124	659,501	3,806,980
Administration	293,398	—	293,398	252,695
	<u>603,775</u>	<u>349,124</u>	<u>952,899</u>	<u>4,059,675</u>
Total expenses	603,775	349,124	952,899	4,059,675
Excess (deficiency) of revenue over expenses				
	20,557	—	20,557	(226,945)
Fund balance, beginning of year	2,477,234	—	2,477,234	2,704,179
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$2,497,791</u>	<u>\$ —</u>	<u>\$2,497,791</u>	<u>\$2,477,234</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral
part of these financial statements.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statement of Cash Flows

for the year ended June 30, 1990
(with comparative totals for 1989)

	<u>1990</u>	<u>Totals</u> <u>1989</u>
Cash flows from operating activities:		
Excess (deficiency) of revenue over expenses	\$ 20,557	\$ (226,945)
Adjustments to reconcile excess (deficiency) of revenue over expenses to net cash (used in) provided by operating activities:		
Amortization of investment discounts	(11,494)	15,145
Decrease in grants receivable	1,027,260	853,340
(Decrease) increase in other assets	21,020	(102,321)
Decrease in deferred revenue	(439,224)	(3,454,003)
Decrease in accounts payable and accrued expenses	(16,073)	(21,978)
Decrease in grants and contracts payable	(264,162)	(35,490)
Total adjustments	<u>317,327</u>	<u>(2,745,307)</u>
Net cash provided by (used in) operating activities	<u>337,884</u>	<u>(2,972,252)</u>
Cash flows from investing activities:		
Purchase of short-term investments	(1,804,674)	(3,496,851)
Sale of short-term investments	1,800,000	398,406
Net cash used in investing activities	<u>(4,674)</u>	<u>(3,098,445)</u>
Net increase (decrease) in cash and cash equivalents	333,210	(6,070,697)
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of the year	<u>457,059</u>	<u>6,527,756</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of the year	<u>\$ 790,269</u>	<u>\$ 457,059</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES

for the year ended June 30, 1990
 (with comparative totals for 1989)

	Research	Access	Bibliography	Librarianship	Library	Total	Administration	Total Expenses	
					Resources and Preservation	Program Expenses		Year ended June 30	
								1990	1989
Unrestricted:									
Grants and contracts	\$ 8,000	\$13,243	\$ 51,975	\$ 23,664	\$ 16,000	\$ 112,882	\$ —	\$112,882	\$ 452,220
Refunds and overappropriations	—	(7,927)	(64,612)	(44,625)	(15,000)	(132,164)	—	(132,164)	(4,671)
Staff and travel	—	6,578	7,267	72,443	(1,508)	84,780	150,266	235,046	247,964
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	—	2,698	41,886	43,052	2,418	90,054	—	90,054	141,964
Board expenses	—	—	—	—	—	—	31,400	31,400	25,092
Office expenses	—	116	—	48	—	164	—	164	93,357
Support services	—	19,332	19,333	96,663	19,333	154,661	111,732	266,393	243,994
	<u>8,000</u>	<u>34,040</u>	<u>55,849</u>	<u>191,245</u>	<u>21,243</u>	<u>310,377</u>	<u>293,398</u>	<u>603,775</u>	<u>1,199,920</u>
Restricted:									
Grants and contracts	148,976	800	—	98,837	—	248,613	—	248,613	2,716,003
Refunds and overappropriations	(53,049)	(1,693)	—	(31,628)	—	(86,370)	—	(86,370)	(38,505)
Staff and travel	41,726	—	—	—	—	41,726	—	41,726	62,029
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	90,791	3,267	—	9,343	—	103,401	—	103,401	61,753
Office expenses	2,881	—	—	208	—	3,089	—	3,089	2,581
Support services	38,665	—	—	—	—	38,665	—	38,665	55,894
	<u>269,990</u>	<u>2,374</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>76,760</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>349,124</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>349,124</u>	<u>2,859,755</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$277,990</u>	<u>\$36,414</u>	<u>\$ 55,849</u>	<u>\$268,005</u>	<u>\$ 21,243</u>	<u>\$ 659,501</u>	<u>\$293,398</u>	<u>\$952,899</u>	<u>\$4,059,675</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

Notes to Financial Statements

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (the Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research.

The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

2. Summary of significant accounting policies

The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below:

Grant revenue

Grants to the Council are recorded in the balance sheet as grants receivable and as deferred grant revenues when awarded. Revenues of restricted grant funds are recognized only to the extent of expenditures that satisfy the restricted purposes of these grants.

Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized as income in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors.

Contributions

Restricted contributions are recorded as deferred revenue when received. Contribution revenue is recognized when the related expenses are incurred.

Grants and contracts payable

Grants and contracts made by the Council are recorded in the balance sheet as grants and contracts payable and as an expense at the time recipients are awarded the grants. Current period expenses are reduced for grant or contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Cash and cash equivalents, and short-term investments

Cash and cash equivalents, which primarily consist of deposits in a money market fund, and short-term investments, which consist of treasury notes, are recorded at cost which approximates market. These balances include restricted amounts of \$1,352,163 and \$1,655,186 at June 30, 1990 and 1989, respectively. Cash equivalents represent invest-

ments with original maturities of 90 days or less. Interest which is not restricted by the related grants is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs identified as support services costs have been allocated to programs and administration on a systematic basis. These costs primarily include salary, benefits, rent and other expenses.

3. Income taxes

The Council, a private operating foundation, is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3).

4. Retirement plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution, net of that reimbursed by the Commission on Preservation and Access (the Commission), was approximately \$49,000 and \$53,000 for fiscal year 1990 and 1989, respectively.

5. Commitments

The Council has entered into a lease agreement for office space which expires in May 1993. The minimum future rental due will be approximately \$172,000 per year through May 1993. As part of this lease agreement, the Council will be assessed an annual charge based on its proportionate share of the increase in the operating costs of the building. For the years ended June 30, 1990 and 1989, rent expense totaled \$139,000 and \$136,000, respectively, of which approximately \$28,000 and \$23,000, respectively, represents the Council's share of the increase in the operating costs.

The Council subleases a portion of its leased office space. Rental income from this sublease amounted to approximately \$35,000 in fiscal years 1990 and 1989.

6. Commission on Preservation and Access

The Commission on Preservation and Access (the Commission) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published

and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information. In 1989, the Council granted to the Commission \$2,067,000 it had received on behalf of the Commission for support of the Commission's preservation program. Also, in 1989, the Council awarded to the Commission a general support grant totaling \$200,000 of which \$133,333 is payable to the Commission at June 30, 1990.

The Council also entered into an agreement with the Commission effective July 1, 1988 under which the Council provides office space, employee services including employee benefits, equipment, supplies and other overhead items to the Commission. Commission staff members are employees of the Council and receive the same benefits as members of the Council. The percentage of shared overhead costs charged to the Commission is negotiated annually. For fiscal year 1990, the Commission's share was 25%. The total amount of expenses and other overhead costs charged to the Commission for fiscal year 1990 amounted to \$356,400. At June 30, 1990 and 1989, the Commission owed the Council \$30,173 and \$54,124, respectively, under the terms of this agreement.

Certain members of the Council's Board of Directors are also members of the Commission's Board of Directors. However, as these members are in the minority and there are no other elements of managerial or financial control, these two entities have not been combined.

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